

Feasibility of Developing Fiber-Reinforced Polymeric Composite Couplers for Hydrogen Transmission Pipelines

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Almost the furthest flight to ICCM

Singapore Institute of Manufacturing Technology

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MTI MINISTRY OF TRADE AND INDUSTRY SINGAPORE

a Agency for Science, Technology and Research SINGAPORE

a Singapore Institute of Manufacturing Technology SIMTech

A world-class innovation partner in advanced manufacturing technologies, systems and capabilities

- Founded in 1993
- SIMTech have 400+ staff, ~90 students

Manufacturing will be Smarter, Greener and More Connected in the Future

Next-Gen Manufacturing Processes

- 4D Additive Manufacturing
- Adaptive Machining & Surface Engineering
- Hybrid & Multi-Materials Forming
- MedTech Manufacturing
- Extreme Manufacturing
- **Advanced Polymer and Composite processing**

Autonomous Manufacturing

Enabling Data-Driven and Knowledge-Based Manufacturing with Workforce Augmentation Technologies

Polymer and Composite Processing Group @ SIMTech

01. Injection Moulding Process

02. Sheet Compression Moulding & Thermoforming

03. Extrusion and Additive Manufacturing

04. Lightweight Design and Process Simulation

- Vacuum Forming
- 2IR Composite Thermoforming
- Compression Moulding
- In-situ consolidation
- In-situ polymerization

□ Polymer Injection Moulding (Auburg Allrounder 570H, 200T, 2500bar, 450°C)

□ Injection Compression Moulding (Witmann Ecopower 110, 110T, 2100bar, 350°C)

□ High Temperature Extruder (Leistritz ZSE 27 MAXX, L/D ratio: 48, screw Diameter: 27mm, 450°C, melt pressure: 220 bar)

□ Integrated Composite Thermoforming (320T-1.2x1.2m 125kW 2IR)

□ Hot Press Sheet Consolidator (60T-40x40cm platen - 450°C, equipped with a water chiller)

□ Vacuum Thermoforming (Formech HD1500, 1.5x1m, x10mm, 55kW quartz heater)

□ Vacuum Thermoforming (CMS eidos se 1.5x1mx10mm, 75kW halogen heater)

□ Microinjection Moulding (Babyplast, 6T, 1850bar, 75x75x70mm mould)

□ Drying oven (Gen lab, 1.6x1.1m sheet size, 50 sheets 250°C)

□ Composites Curing Oven (OV301 - 1070x440x500mm - 200°C)

□ Portable Hot Bonder (Aerofom Composites AHB-380-s, 16 Amp or 32 Amp and 10 thermocouples)

Background: Strategy of Hydrogen Pipeline in Singapore

Hydrogen Value-chain and Status

Singapore's vision:

- ✓ Establish a role of hydrogen in long-term energy strategies
- ✓ Target Net-zero CO₂ emissions by 2050

Low-Carbon Energy Research (LCER) Funding Initiative

- Directed Hydrogen Programme and Emerging Technology Grant
- Phase 1 since 2021 – S\$55 Mil
- Phase 2 since 2024 – S\$55 Mil

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Transforming natural gas delivery system in SG

- Hydrogen transmission and receiving infrastructure is not ready in Singapore. The solution of hydrogen fuel distribution from filling stations or tanks are absent.
- Augmentation of the network such as additional pipelines and larger pipe configurations, would be required to ensure that supply can continue meeting required hydrogen energy demand of end-users.
- One possibility for rapidly expanding the hydrogen delivery infrastructure is to adapt part of the natural gas delivery.
- Both metal and fiber-reinforced composite pipelines are currently used in the gas transmission network in SG. But metal pipeline systems are not suitable for hydrogen due to hydrogen embrittlement.

Background: Review of Existing Pipeline System

Pipeline system	Applications	Materials	Operating pressure	Distribution pressure	Remarks
U.S. Natural Gas (NG) Pipeline [1]	Electric power production and split between residential and commercial uses	Carbon steel, API 5L A, B, X42 and X46	42 – 84 bar (OD 4 inch to 48 inch)	less than 17.2 bar (OD 0.5 inch to 8 inch)	
SG Town Gas (TG)	for industrial, eating houses and residential	Carbon steel X60 05 X65 grade	3 barg	0.5 barg and 0.02 barg	The pipes are internally coated with 75 micron epoxy and 2.5mm, 3-layer Polyethene coating. Welded
SG NG pipeline [2]	for power stations and industrial uses	Carbon steel for operation and PE for distribution	28 and 40 barg	3-6 barg	The Design Pressure is 50 barg and Test Pressure is 62.5 barg.
Strohm thermoplastic composite pipe (TCP)	Suitable for CO2 and Hydrogen transport	Carbon – PVDF Carbon – PA12 Fiberglass - HDPE	Failure at max 689 bar		Grades with different temp limit, 65, 80 and 121 °C.
SoluForce TCP	Hydrogen transmission	Not released	42 bar (OD 4-6 inch)		Flexible pipe system with nonmetal fitting

Current Technology for Pipe Connectivity and Limitations

Metallic coupler with mechanical joints

Compression of O-Ring seals

Failure of O-Ring seals

- A metallic joint with elastomer O-ring seals.
- Lack of durability in H₂.
- O-ring sealing fail during fatigue testing of the structural layer at all pressure levels for hydrogen pipes.

Polymer Electrofusion Coupler

Leakage / Crack at fusion interface

- Metallic coupler with thermoplastic liner, being used in current NG and geothermal pipeline system
- Limited to a very low-pressure pipe system, energy-intensive
- Once the fusion process is completed, the joint is considered permanent and unrepairable

Growing trend of using fibre reinforced thermoplastic (FRTP) composite pipes

Requirements for pipe connectivity

- Sufficient interlayer bonding
- Minimised hydrogen leakage
- Strong durability under thermocycles
- Safe, reliable and cost-effective

We want FRTP composite couplers !

- Weldable
- Impermeable
- Energy-efficient
- Recyclable
- Durable

F RTP Couplers: from Concept Design to Prototyping

Aims at development of a fiber reinforced thermoplastic (F RTP) composite coupler for joining metal and thermoplastic composite pipelines, synergizing robust bonding and pressure resistance

Coupler design concept

Defects in composites part fabricated by resin infusion

Research Scopes

- **In-situ polymerization technology** with infusible resins to achieve the minimised defects.
- Composite coupler formalization: tubular shape, irregular shape, etc..
- **Enhancing material compatibility regarding multiple interface bonding** between the coupler and the metal or F RTP pipelines.
- Advanced simulation techniques for **coupler layup design** and **optimization**.

Preliminary Study on Composite Coupler

- ❑ Composite coupler connecting carbon steel pipe and PE pipe

Pipe assembly fixture

Resin infusion process of the coupler

Some difficulties identified:

- Poor resin penetration and inconsistent flow front.
- Wrinkle and distortion of fabrics after curing
- Non-uniform interface stress transfer between dissimilar materials

Inconsistent resin front

Fabric wrinkle

Proof-of-concept: composite coupler

Solution: It's important to develop **process monitoring system** and **physics-based process simulation model** to improve composite coupler quality.

Development of in-situ polymerization monitoring system

❑ Current solutions

Spot sensors assembled in RTM mold [1]

- Numerous sensors are required to cover whole area, increasing tooling **complexity** and **cost**

Inductively coupled sensor [2]

- Sensor **interference** with the base due to poor material compatibility, reducing structural integrity.

❑ Distributed resistance sensor for resin-infusion monitoring

Methodology:

Electrodes printed on glass fiber via direct ink writing (DIW) with high conductive silver ink

Resistors printed on glass fiber via direct ink writing (DIW) with low conductive carbon ink

- Ultra-thin
- No foreign materials (carbon-based sensors used)
- Minimized influence on resin flow

[1] Pantelulis, Nikos, et al. "Advanced Process Monitoring and Control for CFRP RTM in Aerospace without compromises." SAMPE 2024 (2024).

[2] Chilles, James S., et al. "Monitoring cure and detecting damage in composites with inductively coupled embedded sensors." Composites Science and Technology 134 (2016): 81-88.

Development of in-situ polymerization monitoring system

- Resin front position captured by the distributed resistance sensor

Working principle:
The resistance change when
resin immerse the resistors

Resin flow distance captured by manual
observation and distributed sensors

- Distributed resistance sensors accurately reflect the resin front positions, showing great agreement with physical flow observation.
- The resin front captured by the sensor is for the bottom layer, lagging behind that from the top layer observed. The difference is caused by uneven flow through the fabrics thickness.
- The developed sensor can be used to continuously monitor the resin front distribution.
- More effective than commercial piezoelectric and piezoresistive sensors.

Development of in-situ polymerization monitoring system

- Capacitance sensor for curing status monitoring

- Two curing status were monitored, and their curing characteristics are captured by sensors
- The capacitance during the curing decrease first then increase
- Curing status can be further correlated to the capacitance signals

Infusion Process Analysis (Moldex3D)

Flow complexity and the needs of process simulations

- ❑ The placement of inlet and outlet is needed to be optimised for infusion over a tubular shape. Process simulation model was hence developed.
- ❑ It is challenging to evaluate effects of fibre layup orientation, peel plies and distribution media, while a homogenous flow model lacks of accuracy.
- ❑ Flow inconsistency at top and bottom layers were captured, yet to be further validated with experiments.

Fiber layup stacking sequence defined

Parameters	Values
K_{xx} (From Literature)	$1.743 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$
K_{xx} (Calculated)	$1.211 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$
K_{DM} (From Literature)	$1.94 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2$
K_{DM} (Calculated)	$1.038 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2$

Explicit numerical flow simulation models with and without distribution media (DM)

$$L^2(t) = \frac{2 \cdot K \cdot P \cdot t}{\eta \cdot \phi}$$

(Rouhi et al., 2022)

- Tubular shape model showed different flow front time between top and bottom surfaces indicated the through-thickness flow penetration

- Flat sample studies concluded that mesh sensitivity was insignificant regarding number of elements across the thickness of both the distribution media and laminates.
- We verified that back calculated permeability values K are needed instead of citing input permeability values from literatures.
- More studies are on-going to add more detailed settings regarding K values for peel ply and porosity ϕ

Numerical Design for Composite Couplers

- ❑ Direct end-to-end joining with composite coupler
 - Adhesive bonding between the coupler and the pipes
 - Coupler with plain weave composite
- ❑ Finite-element progressive failure modelling
 - Cohesive interaction between the coupler and the pipes
 - Cohesive interaction at the two ends of the pipes

Bending and **axial tension** are identified as two critical loading cases.

- Delamination between the coupler and pipes happens in these two cases.
- Both the bonding strength and the composite lay-up need to be considered in the coupler design

Composite coupler is not easy to fail under inner pressure and torsion

Critical Load Cases

Summary And Future Work

Summary

- ❖ The development of FRTP coupler is of great significance to ensure a reliable connectivity for hydrogen transmission pipeline.
- ❖ The in-situ polymerization monitoring system was developed, including distributed resistance sensors for resin front monitoring, and a interdigitated capacitance sensor for resin polymerization monitoring.
- ❖ Critical loading cases of composite coupler were identified and process simulation models were established.

Future work:

- ❖ To develop optimal coupler structural design considering the critical loading cases.
- ❖ To improve the in-situ polymerization quality for coupler by simulation-assisted process optimization.
- ❖ To study the interface behaviour between composite coupler and heterogeneous materials.

Welcome to ICCM25 in Singapore

THANK YOU

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